

ANALYSIS AND IMPROVEMENT OF THE MARKETING ENVIRONMENT AT "ENESSES" LLC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116233>

Abstract. This article covers the concept of marketing, wholesale trade activities, strengthening customer relations, digital marketing, advertising through social networks, and development of a marketing plan is considered.

Keywords: space, marketing environment, concept, wholesale, market, demand, advertising, brand.

Introduction. During the years of independence, there are many problems that need to be implemented in the field of trade, especially in the field of wholesale trade, despite the fact that positive property and organizational changes have taken place. The main reason for this is the market mechanism of the activities of wholesale trade entities in the current conditions, in their activities modern service use of economic levers, marketing and market opportunities, scope of service, communication links, relations with other economic sectors, improvement of its management and state regulation mechanisms.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing activities and their practical application, including F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. We can include famous scientists like Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the research carried out in the field of marketing in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. R. Ibragimov to them. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, SH. A. Musayeva and others can be included. The marketing environment is a set of market participants, external forces and processes that operate outside the company in the market and affect the company's ability to establish and maintain successful partnerships with its target customers. Any company operates and succeeds in a certain environment, not in a vacuum. Marketing environment means a set of entities and forces that directly affect the establishment of good cooperative relations with customers of the company's marketing service employees and the maintenance of these relations. The marketing environment consists of a set of forces and factors that directly affect the market situation in general and enterprise activity in particular, including other market subjects.

The main goal of the analysis of the internal environment of the enterprise is to study the factors that determine the potential of the enterprise and influence it. The following elements of the internal environment were studied in the study of enterprise activity.

Management organization structure, division of labor, study and management of customer activities, working with CRM systems, functionally and hierarchically, centralization, procedures and methods of making key decisions, control of decision implementation, management information system, communication processes, type of management, professional nature and level of senior management, strategic planning system.

Production departments (number, specialists, capacity), the volume of goods offered depending on the current state of the leased or own production base, the type of technology used, the organization of customer service, warehouse capacity, product quality control making, non-threatening provision, production (packing, wrapping) power, direct losses in service. It is also important to assess the level of full utilization of production capacity. In marketing applied strategies, market (big and small, position, competitors), customers, enterprise image, enterprise goods, price, sales and communication policy, information supply situation and organization, mutual marketing relations, internal marketing, advertising and its structures, activities of moving products and goods, etc. Financial and economic department business assets, equity and debt capital, credit facilities, business liquidity, capital turnover and liquidity, capital planning, gross income, profit and utilization. One of the important indicators of enterprise activity is its profitability. It is calculated according to the ratio of the received income indicator (sales volume, gross income, working capital to production, cost of fixed assets, etc.). Personnel department composition and qualification, professional and qualification level, personnel formation policy (planning, selection and temporary hiring, dismissal, unemployment, etc.), personnel development (professional orientation and retraining, certification and evaluation, testing of new employees conducting, ensuring growth in the service process), organizing and motivating work, applying relations between employees, etc.

The enterprise is engaged in wholesale trade activities, and the situation of the wholesale trade market was also considered.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Table 1

The main indicators of wholesale trade in our country

Indicators	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Wholesale turnover - total, bln. soum	22001.6	26749.1	30413.0	38301.6	42185.9	63528.5	93322.8	120451.1	172,790.1
Stocks (by the end of the year) total, bln. soum	5175.3	6659.3	7780.1	9489.9	10763.3	13166.7	14316.5	22367.4	29,572.5
on days of turnover	85.0	90.0	92.0	89.0	92.0	75.0	55.0	67.0	62.0
Growth rate of wholesale trade turnover, in percentage compared to last year	109.1	111.0	107.1	116.5	94.0	126.8	128.6	113.6	128.5

As can be seen from this table, year-by-year indicators of wholesale trade turnover, stock of goods and turnover of goods are given.

Analysis and results The company always pays serious attention to marketing. After all, being a wholesale company, it always deals with customers. This implies the constant development of relations with marketing. If we look at the state of organization of marketing activities in the company's activities, the organization of marketing services is used in the company according to the 4 main organizational structures of marketing, market-oriented and product-oriented organizational structures. And its structure is as follows.

The organizational structure of the marketing service based on the production of goods allows enterprises to better adapt to the market requirements for each product and to produce goods with different production technologies, a short life cycle, and high innovation requirements .

Figure 1. The organizational structure of the marketing service in the enterprise based on the production of goods

A market-oriented organizational structure of a marketing service in an enterprise is a type of marketing management structure in which managers of individual markets are responsible for the development and implementation of strategies and plans for marketing activities in specific markets. The market-oriented organizational structure of the marketing service is illustrated in the diagram below (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Market-oriented organizational structure of the marketing service.

Currently, the ethical aspects of marketing activities are constantly discussed by both the media and the companies themselves, for example, in the development of internal corporate policies, customer service policies, brand promotion in social networks, etc. But most of the time these discussions are just discussions, and even then, all companies follow the law and fulfill their obligations.

It was found that three main aspects are distinguished in the functions performed by marketers in the enterprise:

Direct professional activity ethics - marketing is to refrain from the production and resale of dangerous, harmful products, to provide high-quality products and services, and to be honest with customers.

Marketing ethics in advertising campaigns - honesty, dissemination of correct information, respectful attitude towards consumers and competitors (no print, intrusive advertising formats, ambiguous messages, black PR, refrain from insulting any group of people to attract attention drag).

Marketing research ethics - respect for confidentiality, respect for personal data, respect for respondents and data collection personnel.

In studying the activity of the enterprise, the working status of marketing concepts and its availability were studied. In particular, the company's purposeful use of the concept of sales and marketing attracted my attention. That is, while the enterprise is engaged in wholesale trade today, attention is being paid to further strengthening relations with customers, to fully satisfy its capabilities, and to intensify the relationship of marketing experts to their work. In addition, digital marketing concepts are also being used to receive orders. Advertisements and discounts are being announced through social networks.

Today, as a result of increasing attention to marketing activities, the company has developed a marketing plan, which is formulated as follows.

Table 2

Marketing plan of "Enesses" LLC

Sections	Content
Enter	Brief summaries in plan sections
1. Market situation and its prospects	Analysis of information about the marketing environment, consumers, competitors and their goods, sales channels.
2. Analysis of enterprise opportunities	Contributing factors and risk assessment.
3. Financial and marketing goals and objectives	Net profit, sales volume, market share, price level, advertising coverage and other indicators.
4. Implementation of marketing strategy	Problems, ways to solve them and options.
5. Action program	What to do? When? Who is responsible for this? What should be the result? How much does it cost? answers to the questions are found.
6. Budgets	Comparison of results and costs
7. Control and ordering	Analysis of effectiveness and conducting activities to change the actions in the plan.

In the study of enterprise activity, I focused mainly on working with data on the wholesale trade of food products.

Table 3

Information on sales of food products of "Enesses" LLC in 2020-2022

No	Food products	Unit of measure	2021 year	2022 year	2023* year
1.	Flour products	thousand soums	12387.4	14682.1	16497.3
2.	Pasta products	thousand soums	4387.6	7624.3	10203.5
3.	Meat and sausage products	thousand soums	16348.2	17863.7	18164.8
4.	Processed and fermented dairy products	thousand soums	389.2	863.4	1005.4
5.	Ice cream and soft drinks	thousand soums	6892.1	10204.1	10043.6
6.	Caramel and candy products	thousand soums	10657.3	11826.0	9183.2
7.	Other products	thousand soums	35683.2	29591.6	33633.9
	Total	thousand soums	86745.0	92655.2	98731.7

As can be seen from the table, in the retail turnover of "Enesses" LLC, of the main food products, flour products are 14,682.1 thousand soums (2022), pasta products are 7,624.3 thousand soums (2022), meat and sausage products 17,863.7 thousand soums (year 2022), processed and fermented milk products 863.4 thousand soums (year 2022), caramel and candy products 11,826.0 thousand soums (year 2022) is organizing.

Apart from trade, one of the main activities of the enterprise is the provision of household services and services. Today, the enterprise provides the following services to the population:

hairdressing, manicure services; tailoring and tailoring services; telephone, electronic goods repair services; PayNet services; Transport services and others.

Table 4

Status of providing household paid services to the population of "Enesses" LLC in 2020-2022

No	Service types	Unit of measure	2021 year	2022 year	2023* year
1.	Transport services	thousand soums	63491.3	66237.2	67436.1
2.	Telephone, electronic goods repair services	thousand soums	623.4	649.1	964.2
3.	PayNet services	thousand soums	6482.4	6528.4	6829.1
	Total	thousand soums	78509.3	81254.4	123869.3

As can be seen from the table, the enterprise also provides services to the population. In particular, by the end of 2022, transport services worth 66,237.2 thousand soums, telephone and electronic goods repair services worth 649.1 thousand soums, PayNet services worth 6528.4 thousand soums have been provided.

Price policy of the enterprise: when concluding a sales contract, suppliers and buyers must determine the price at which the product will be sold. The price of the goods is determined by the department of planning and economy based on the cost of production. Calculation is done for each product. There is a strict rule when determining the price: the price should not be lower than the cost. In addition to costs, the price includes statutory taxes. When calculating the selling price of a product unit, the following costs are allocated and the following approaches are used:

Table 5

Costs in calculating the selling price of a product unit

No	Name of cost items	Calculation method
<i>Direct costs</i>		
1.	Raw material	Discounted prices
1.1	Raw material	Raw materials are the basic and additional resources necessary for the production of products. Baked clay, soil and cheperitsa are the main raw materials for construction products.
1.2	Supporting materials	As per direct material consumption rates approved by Chief Engineer
2.	Water	In accordance with the norms of water and heat energy consumption approved by the Chief Engineer.
3.	Salaries of key production employees:	It includes the wages of production workers and other workers directly related to the production of products, performance of work and provision of services, as well as payments for time not worked (absent) stipulated by the labor legislation.
<i>Additional costs</i>		
4.	Additional costs	Accounting is carried out in the conditions of production facilities that produce certain types of products and semi-finished products.
5.	Common usage costs	Accounting is maintained for the entire company. The apportionment method is applied in direct proportion to the wages of the main production workers for each type of product, work and service.
6.	Shipping costs	If necessary, according to the contract, the sale price can be calculated taking into account the costs associated with their transportation. In this case, the transport costs in the calculation are allocated as a separate article.

Cost analysis is the most important cost management tool. Its main goal is to identify opportunities for more rational use of production resources, reduce production and sales costs, and ensure profit growth. Dynamic analysis of cost indicators allows to evaluate changes in production and financial activity of the enterprise, to forecast for the future.

The grouping of costs by elements is unified and mandatory, and allows controlling the formation, structure and dynamics of costs through systems that describe their economic content. It is necessary to study the ratio of actual and past labor, to standardize and analyze inventories, to calculate specific indicators of the turnover of working capital, and to study other calculations of the industrial and general economic level. The analysis of the elemental composition and structure of production costs allows determining the main directions of searching for reserves depending on the level of material, labor and capital intensity of production.

Table 6

Costs of sales activities at the enterprise in 2021-2022 and their dynamics

Cost elements	2021 year		2022 year	
	All, million. soum	Specificity in trading costs, %	All, million. soum	Specificity in trading costs, %
Material costs:	35000	73.22	50700	77.29
raw material	31000	64.85	45000	68.60
energy resources	4000	8.37	5700	8.69
labor costs	10000	20.9	11500	17.5
contributions for social needs	3200	6.7	3300	5.0
Depreciation	450	0.9	510	0.8
other expenses	1380	2.9	1800	2.7
Trading expenses, total	47800	100	65600	100
Products for sale	49600		68600	

To a greater extent, this indicator provides a clear correlation with profit: an increase in costs leads to a decrease in profit per ruble of production, and vice versa. Among its disadvantages, this indicator can be affected by many subjective and objective factors, that is, it does not depend on the quality of work of the enterprise team.

Selling manufactured products is also considered as an important marketing activity.

The range of products will also expand during the sales process. Every enterprise is required to have its own sales channels in the organization of product sales.

As sales channels, intermediaries who take ownership of goods participate in the delivery of products from the producer to the consumer.

Today, most businesses are setting up sales outlets on their balance sheet to sell their products. In general, the importance of wholesale trade enterprises in the delivery of goods to the final consumer is increasing.

This prevents the transfer of goods to other persons. It will have the ability to control the competition and influence the buyers.

"Enesses" LLC is currently working with a number of sales intermediaries.

Most of the trade intermediaries are located in cities and districts such as Samarkand city, Samarkand district, Jomboy district, Okdarya district and Pstdargom district. Data on wholesale goods sold through the main 6 sales intermediaries of "Enesses" LLC in 2020-2022 are presented in Table 5.

Table 7

"Enesses" LLC main sales intermediaries and information about selling goods through them

No	Main indicators	Unit of measure	2021	2022	2023*
1	"Abdisait Trade" LLC	thousand soums	432.1	462.4	407.6
2	YATT "Djabborov Alisher Ashurovich"	thousand soums	96.3	104.1	113.2
3	"Ozodbek Universal Trade" LLC	thousand soums	736.9	1104.2	1436.2
4	"Samarkand Gem Star" LLC	thousand soums	1462.3	1643.7	2432.3
5	"Riskiyabanu universal trade" LLC	thousand soums	237.4	361.6	401.3
6	"Doston Mashal Service" LLC	thousand soums	70.6	84.2	101.6
	Total		3035.6	3760.2	4892.2

If we pay attention to the data of the table, the trade volume of "Samarkand Gavhar Yulduzi" LLC and "Ozodbek Universal Trade" LLC is high in terms of trade turnover of construction brick goods.

I studied the results of the employees' activity, characteristics of labor resources of "Enesses" LLC. That is, the goods sold by the enterprise, labor resources of the enterprise, economic indicators were analyzed.

Table 8

Dynamics of labor resources of "Enesses" LLC

No	Indicators	Unit of measure	2021	2022	2023*	The ratio of 2022 to 2021	
						+;-	percent, %
1.	Average number of employees	person	48	56	65	+8	116.6
2.	Average monthly salary of employees	thousand soums	4 966.0	4 771.0	5 309.0	-195	96.0
3.	Labor productivity	thousand soums	40585	50789	65888	+10204	125.1

As can be seen from the table, the total number of employees of "Enesses" LLC will be 56 by the end of 2022, which has increased by 8 compared to 2021. Labor productivity increased by 125.1 percent or 1.25 times. In 2022, the production volume per capita increased from 40,585,000 to 50,789,000 soums. In 2022, the average monthly salary of employees decreased from 4,966,000 soums to 4,771,000 soums, that is, it increased by 96.0%.

5 marketers and 5 sales department employees work in the company's marketing service department. Their share in the total number of employees is also good. After all, in today's rapidly

developing era, the role of marketing is incomparable. For this reason, the marketing department also operates in this enterprise.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

We believe that it is appropriate to carry out the following tasks in order to improve and develop trade activities in the enterprise:

- creation of economic and legal opportunity to sell cheap and high-quality products to the population;
- creation of mechanisms for the development of the process of integration and cooperation in the fields of production, trade and other services;
- creation of an effective mechanism of state regulation of production and trade;
- activation and acceleration of activities of production organizations protecting consumer rights;
- improvement of logistic systems in enterprise activity;
- improving the quality of after-sales service and improving timely service;
- be active in social networks and promote your brand
- ensure mass formation of a competitive environment in the trade sector

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